

A Study to Develop Empiric Antibacterial Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcers in Rural India

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Abstract

Introduction: In order to evaluate the clinical features, range of microbial flora, antibiotic susceptibility, and develop an empiric antimicrobial therapy, this study was conducted on patients with diabetic foot ulcers (DFU).

Method: Between December 2020 and November 2021, clinical information and tissue samples were gathered from 100 diabetic foot ulcer patients. Clinical and microbiological data was evaluated after the samples were handled in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute recommendations.

Results: Males in their fourth and fifth decades of life had the highest prevalence of DFU in this sample of 100 patients. The majority of patients experienced neuropathy and poor glycemic control. Gram-negative bacteria made up 73.6% of the 105 bacterial isolates isolated from 96 samples, while Gram-positive bacteria made up 27.2%. The majority of samples (48.5%) revealed the growth of a single bacterium, followed by the growth of two bacteria and polymicrobial growth in 28.5% and 15.1%, respectively, of tissue samples. The most common isolation (27.2%) was *Pseudomonas*, which is responsive to imipenem (91%), amikacin (86.5%), gentamicin (83.2%), and cefotaxime (81%). *Staphylococcus aureus* (19.0%) is the next most common isolate, and it is sensitive to amikacin and gentamicin (99%), as well as ofloxacin (91%). Ampicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, *Proteus*, and *Klebsiella* were all very resistant to these medications.

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that DFU are typical in the fourth and fifth decades of life. Most infectious organisms are gram-negative bacteria. The majority of bacteria, both Gram positive and Gram negative, are sensitive to aminoglycosides and have varying degrees of resistance to routinely used antibiotics. DFU infections can be treated with amikacin and gentamicin as empiric antibiotics.

Keywords: Antibiotic sensitivity, Central India, diabetic foot ulcer, empiric treatment, infection

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Introduction

With over 62 million diabetics, diabetes is quickly assuming the status of a possible epidemic in India [1]. The prevalence of diabetes varies by area in India, from 5.3% in the center to 13.6% in the north [2]. Since diabetes is not a condition that must be reported, the true cost of the disease in India may be underestimated [3]. Foot ulceration is one of the most prevalent complications of diabetes, affecting 15% of diabetic individuals over the course of their lifetime, according to estimates. The prevalence of DFU ranges from 4% to 10%, and infections, which account for 40% to 80% of cases, are the most frequent cause of morbidity and mortality in (DFU) [4]. For the treatment of DFU infections, antimicrobials are initially chosen based on empirical criteria. Antibiotic resistance has emerged as a common problem in healthcare institutions as a result of the decreasing number of innovative antibiotics being discovered and the rash usage of antibiotics that are already accessible [5]. The issue confronted by doctors in treating these patients is exacerbated by the fact that diabetic nephropathy affects around one-third of diabetic patients and by the rising occurrence of infections that are multidrug resistant in DFU [6]. The purpose of this study was to identify the clinical and microbiological characteristics of DFU patients, identify the microorganisms' patterns of antibiotic susceptibility in these patients, and develop an empiric antibiotic regimen.

Methodology:

100 DFU patients attending the diabetic foot clinic were recruited for this prospective and observational study at a tertiary care teaching hospital between December 2020 and November 2021. The

institutional ethical committee approved the study. All study participants provided their written, informed permission. A diabetic foot ulcer (DFU), as defined by the International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF), is a full-thickness wound that penetrates the dermis below the ankle in a diabetic patient [7]. Foot ulcers were rated according to the Meggitt Wagner Classification System into six classes (grade 0–grade 5). Following proper consent, all patients' basic demographic information was gathered and recorded into an excel spreadsheet. Each study participant provided a thorough medical history, including information on their current complaint, the length of their diabetes, personal smoking and alcohol use patterns, and their diabetic foot self-care routines. Semmes Weinstein monofilament test results were used to determine sensory neuropathy. On the foot's sole, the 5.07 Semmes Weinstein monofilament's feel was evaluated. At a spot on the sole of the foot that was perpendicular to the skin, monofilament was placed, and pressure was applied until it bent under the weight of 10 grams. It was noted as abnormal when the patient was unable to detect the monofilament at one or more locations [9]. Results of blood tests were documented in an excel spreadsheet. Whenever the serum creatinine level was 1.5 mg/dL or more, nephropathy was deemed to be present. Both fasting blood glucose levels greater than or equal to 125 and HbA1c levels equal to or greater than 6 were regarded as abnormal. To avoid picking up surface colonisation flora, the wound was cleaned, washed extensively with saline, and any slough or exudate was debrided before the tissue culture specimen was collected in the minor operation room. After scraping the ulcer base or deep portion of the

wound edge with a sterile curette and obtaining incised tissue specimens of about 0.5 millimetres from various wound sites, specimens were collected in sterile culture bottles containing normal saline. More accurate microbiological cultures can be obtained from deep tissue samples collected after curetting [10] than from swab samples. Aerobic bacteria were isolated, identified, and processed using conventional procedures. After being homogenised, the tissue samples were inoculated on Blood and MacConkey agar. These samples were incubated for 24-48 hours at 37 degrees centigrade in an aerobic environment. Applying Kirby Bauer's disc diffusion technique method as outlined in the Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute guideline 2012 [11], colonies were collected, and antibiotic sensitivity was assessed. MS EXCEL was used to input the microbiological culture-sensitivity results into the master chart. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the statistical study, which involved the Chi-square test. $P < 0.05$ is deemed to be a significant level of analysis using the software program SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solutions) 17.0 and Graph Pad Prism 6.0.

Results:

100 DFU participants were enrolled in the trial. There were 100 patients in all, with 70 (69.3%) men and 30 (30.45%) women; the male to female ratio was 2.2:1. The age groups 44–55 years and 54–65 years had the highest percentage of instances (27.5% each), followed by 64–75 years (21%), 34–45 years (16.1%), and 74–85 years (8.5%). The population's average age was 57.55

12.4 years. Males were 51.15 ± 10.1 years old, and females were 58.15 ± 12.5 years old. 81% of the cases in this study came from rural areas, and only 19% were from urban areas. The majority of the study subjects (63.7%), who had ulcers for more than a month, had diabetes for more than nine years. Of the remaining study participants, 49.4% had ulcers for less than a month. In 23.7% of patients, there was a history of regular alcohol consumption, and 41% of people smoked or chewed tobacco. In 16.1% of our cases, diabetic foot self-care was observed. The most frequent symptom was foot numbness (68.5%), followed by foot pain (51.3%) and pedal edoema (51.3%). Claimants made claims in 29.4% of the cases. The majority of patients (88.5%) and patients (76.1%) had abnormal fasting blood sugar levels and abnormal serum HbA1c levels. 40% of cases had nephropathy, with Wagner's grade 2 ulcer being the most prevalent (40.94%), followed by grade 3 (31.3%), grade 5, (16.1%), and grade 4 (11.3%). In 62.8% of the patients, loss of perception of 5.06 Semmes Weinstein monofilaments was observed, suggesting sensory peripheral neuropathy.

In this study, 7.61% of the culture samples were sterile, 48.5% of the samples indicated the growth of a single organism, 28.5% of the samples showed the growth of two organisms, and 15.1% of the tissue samples showed the growth of multiple organisms. According to **Table 1**, *Pseudomonas* (27.2%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (19.04%), and *E coli* (15.4%) were the three most prevalent single bacterial isolates.

Table 1: Bacterial isolates on the basis of growth on culture media and gram-stain.

Isolates	Tissue Culture	No. of Isolates	Percentage (%)
Gram- Positive (27.2%)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19	19.04%
	<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	4	4.4%
	<i>Enterococcus</i>	3	3.80%
Gram-Negative (73.8%)	<i>Acinatobacter</i>	7	7.3%
	<i>Psedomonas</i>	29	27.2%
	<i>Citrobacter kosari</i>	4	4.4%

	<i>E. coli</i>	16	15.4%
	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	7	7.2%
	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	12	11.7%

In this investigation, *Staphylococcus aureus* was susceptible to ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin (81% each), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (74%), ofloxacin (91%), vancomycin (84%), and Clindamycin (71%), and other Gram-positive bacteria were 99% susceptible to amikacin and gentamicin.

In the current study, *Pseudomonas* was responsive to cefotaxime (81%), imipenem (91%), amikacin (86.5%), and gentamicin (83.2%). Ceftriaxone (66.66%) and ceftazidime (71%) were additional powerful antibiotics. Imipenem (94.0%), amikacin (88.1%), ceftazidime (82.2%), cefotaxime (76.3%), gentamycin (76.3%), ceftriaxone (70.4%), and ofloxacin (70.4%) were the antibiotics that were most efficient against *E. coli*. Amikacin (99% each), imipenem (99% each), cefotaxime (83 and 99%, respectively), and gentamicin (84.5 and 87.4%, respectively) were all extremely toxic to *Proteus* and *Klebsiella*. Ampicillin and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid were ineffective against *Pseudomonas*, *E. coli*, *Proteus*, and *Klebsiella*. Ciprofloxacin was highly effective against *Acinetobacter* (99% sensitivity), but ceftriaxone, ceftazidime, gentamicin, amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and ofloxacin were all ineffective. Ceftazidime (61%) and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (99%) were both effective against *Citrobacter*.

Discussion:

One of the most incapacitating consequences for diabetics is foot ulcer. Diabetes is a factor in over half of all lower extremity amputations. The most frequent cause of diabetic lower limb amputation, second only to gangrene, is foot infection [4]. When diabetic foot infections develop, antibiotic treatment is initiated based on the suspected aetiology

of the infection. The final course of action is subsequently amended in light of the bacterial culture and sensitivity report. Depending on the severity of the infection, the course of treatment can last anywhere between 1-2 weeks and more than 4 weeks [12]. The issue confronted by doctors in treating these patients is exacerbated by the fact that diabetic nephropathy affects around one-third of diabetic patients and by the rising occurrence of infections that are multidrug resistant in DFU [6].

The average patient age in this study was 57.55 years. The majority of patients were between the ages of 44 and 65, and the male to female ratio was 2.27, which is comparable to the study done by Yerat et al [4]. In this study, similar to the study of Shahi et al., 81% of patients were from the rural area where this clinic was located, and 19% were from the urban area. [13] According to studies by Maskari et al. [14] and Gadepalli et al. [15], the majority of patients (63.81%) with DFU had diabetes for more than 10 years. A comparable study from South Ethiopia by Deribe et al. [16] reported self-care behaviours in 55.1% of the participants, whereas Mamo et al. [17] reported it in 4.5% of the subjects. Diabetic foot self-care activities were detected in 16.2% of the subjects. The variance in the geographic location of the research sample may explain the variation in self-care activities between these two studies. A total of 100 cases were included in the current investigation, and 53 (51.3%) of those individuals had DFU for more than a month while 48.5% had it for less than a month, which was consistent with studies by Kaur et al. [18] and Alva et al. [19]. Both the current study and Boyko et al. found numbness in 74.1% and 68.5% of the patients, respectively [20]. While Jiang et al. [21] identified pedal edema in 36.3% of cases, this study

found it in 51.3% of cases. In this study, foot discomfort was a symptom in 51.4% of individuals, whereas Boyko et al. [20] reported it in 66.1% of cases. Claudication was discovered in 31.4% of cases in this study, 20.5% in Jiang et al study's [21] and 22.2% in Boyko et al study [20] studies.

Gram-negative bacilli are frequently the cause of diabetic foot infections in India [22]. Numerous research from the West, such as Mendes et al [23] show that Gram positive microbes predominate in diabetic foot ulcers. [24] The difference between the predominance of Gram-negative and Gram-positive organisms in the East and West is mostly unknown. However, Turhan et al. [25] hypothesised that environmental variables, such as hygienic practises like washing hands with faecal flora-contaminated water after defecation, may contribute to higher rates of Gram-negative infections in the poor world than in the West [25,26].

Conclusion:

According to the study's findings, DFU are typical among patients in their fourth and fifth decades of life. Most DFU patients have poor glycemic control, neuropathy, and a considerable number also have nephropathy. A very small percentage of DFU patients also take care of their own feet when they have diabetes. The majority of infections are caused by gram-negative bacteria. In DFU, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas* are the most prevalent Gram-positive and Gram-negative infectious bacteria, respectively. Both Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria are responsive to aminoglycosides due to the community's lower use of injectable aminoglycosides, whereas extensive resistance has grown in the community to routinely prescribed extended spectrum penicillin and cephalosporins. The use of empiric antibiotic therapy for diabetic foot infections has to be reevaluated. Since the majority of the participants in this study were from rural regions, we advise primary care physicians and specialists to

consider Amikacin and gentamicin as the first-line empiric treatments for infected DFU until a definitive course of action based on sensitivity pattern is initiated. Injectable aminoglycosides have been recommended in this study as the first line empiric antimicrobial therapy for the treatment of all diabetic foot infections in this area. By not using antibiotics that are resistant when they don't need to, this will help patients pay less.

References:

1. Joshi SR, Parikh RM. India; the diabetes capital of the world: Now heading towards hypertension. Journal-Association of Physicians of India. 2007 May 1;55(Y):323.
2. Anjana RM, Pradeepa R, Deepa M, Datta M, Sudha V, Unnikrishnan R, Bhansali A, Joshi SR, Joshi PP, Yajnik CS, Dhandhanika VK. Prevalence of diabetes and prediabetes (impaired fasting glucose and/or impaired glucose tolerance) in urban and rural India: Phase I results of the Indian Council of Medical Research-India DIABetes (ICMR-INDIAB) study. *Diabetologia*. 2011 Dec; 54(12):3022-7.
3. Singh AK, Yeola M, Singh N, Damke S. A study on diabetic foot ulcers in Central rural India to formulate empiric antimicrobial therapy. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2020 Aug;9(8):4216.
4. Yerat RC, Rangasamy VR. A clinicomicrobial study of diabetic foot ulcer infections in South India. *International Journal of Medicine and Public Health*. 2015;5(3).
5. Chen J, Min R, Wang H, Zhao S, Li H, Fang P. Trends and drivers of inpatient antibiotic consumption among 89 China tertiary general hospitals from 2011Q1 to 2015Q4. *BioMed research international*. 2018 Nov 1;2018.
6. Keane WF, Brenner BM, De Zeeuw D, Grunfeld JP, McGill J, Mitch WE, Ribeiro AB, Shahinfar S, Simpson RL,

- Snapinn SM, Toto R. The risk of developing end-stage renal disease in patients with type 2 diabetes and nephropathy: the RENAAL study. *Kidney international*. 2003 Apr 1;63(4):1499-507.
7. Bakker K, Apelqvist J, Lipsky BA, Van Netten JJ, Schaper NC, International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF). The 2015 IWGDF guidance documents on prevention and management of foot problems in diabetes: development of an evidence-based global consensus. *Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews*. 2016 Jan; 32:2-6.
 8. Wagner Jr FW. The dysvascular foot: a system for diagnosis and treatment. *Foot & ankle*. 1981 Sep;2(2):64-122.
 9. Boulton AJ, Armstrong DG, Albert SF, Frykberg RG, Hellman R, Kirkman MS, Lavery LA, LeMaster JW, Mills Sr JL, Mueller MJ, Sheehan P. Comprehensive foot examination and risk assessment: a report of the task force of the foot care interest group of the American Diabetes Association, with endorsement by the American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists. *Diabetes care*. 2008 Aug 1;31(8):1679-85.
 10. Senneville É, Lipsky BA, Abbas ZG, Aragón-Sánchez J, Diggie M, Embil JM, Kono S, Lavery LA, Malone M, van Asten SA, Urbančič-Rovan V. Diagnosis of infection in the foot in diabetes: a systematic review. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*. 2020 Mar;36:e3281.
 11. Abdulrazak A, Bitar ZI, Al-Shamali AA, Mobasher LA. Bacteriological study of diabetic foot infections. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications*. 2005 May 1;19(3):138-41.
 12. Grigoropoulou P, Eleftheriadou I, Jude EB, Tentolouris N. Diabetic foot infections: an update in diagnosis and management. *Current diabetes reports*. 2017 Jan;17(1):1-2.
 13. Shahi SK, Kumar A, Kumar S, Singh SK, Gupta SK, Singh TB. Prevalence of diabetic foot ulcer and associated risk factors in diabetic patients from North India. *The journal of diabetic foot complications*. 2012;4(3):83-91.
 14. Al-Maskari F, El-Sadig M. Prevalence of risk factors for diabetic foot complications. *BMC family practice*. 2007 Dec;8(1):1-9.
 15. Gadepalli R, Dhawan B, Sreenivas V, Kapil A, Ammini AC, Chaudhry R. A clinico-microbiological study of diabetic foot ulcers in an Indian tertiary care hospital. *Diabetes care*. 2006 Aug 1;29(8):1727-32.
 16. Deribe B, Woldemichael K, Nemera G. Prevalence and factors influencing diabetic foot ulcer among diabetic patients attending Arbaminch Hospital, South Ethiopia. *J Diabetes Metab*. 2014;5(1):1-7.
 17. Mamo T, Yifter H, Lemessa T. Risk factors assessment of diabetic foot ulcer using the sixty seconds screening tool: a hospital based cross-sectional study at Tikur Anbessa specialized Hospital. *Ethiop Med J*. 2015 Jul 1;2: 45-9.
 18. Kaur N, Kaur N, Kumar R, Gill AK. Clinical and susceptibility profile from diabetic foot patients in tertiary care hospital. *Scholars J Appl Med Sci*. 2014;2(2D):865-9.
 19. Alva KA, Aithala PS, Rai R, Rekha B. Clinical and microbiological profile of diabetic foot in patients admitted at a tertiary care center in Mangalore. *Muller Journal of Medical Sciences and Research*. 2013 Jan 1;4(1):3.
 20. Boyko EJ, Ahroni JH, Stensel VI, Forsberg RC, Davignon DR, Smith DG. A prospective study of risk factors for diabetic foot ulcer. The Seattle Diabetic Foot Study. *Diabetes care*. 1999 Jul 1;22(7):1036-42.
 21. Jiang Y, Ran X, Jia L, Yang C, Wang P, Ma J, Chen B, Yu Y, Feng B, Chen L, Yin H. Epidemiology of type 2 diabetic foot problems and predictive

- factors for amputation in China. The international journal of lower extremity wounds. 2015 Mar;14(1):19-27.
22. Boulton AJ, Armstrong DG, Kirsner RS, Attinger CE, Lavery LA, Lipsky BA, Mills JL, Steinberg JS. Diagnosis and management of diabetic foot complications. *Compendia*. 2018 Oct 1;2018(2).
 23. Mendes JJ, Marques-Costa A, Vilela C, Neves J, Candeias N, Cavaco-Silva P, Melo-Cristino J. Clinical and bacteriological survey of diabetic foot infections in Lisbon. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2012 Jan 1;95(1):153-61.
 24. Seth A, Attri AK, Kataria H, Kochhar S, Seth SA, Gautam N. Clinical profile and outcome in patients of diabetic foot infection. *International Journal of Applied and Basic Medical Research*. 2019 Jan;9(1):14.
 25. Turhan V, Mutluoglu M, Acar A, Hatipoglu M, Onem Y, Uzun G, Ay H, Oncul O, Gorenek L. Increasing incidence of Gram-negative organisms in bacterial agents isolated from diabetic foot ulcers. *The Journal of Infection in Developing Countries*. 2013 Oct 15;7(10):707-12.
 26. Balde A. K., A, T. J., MD S., TM B., A M., K B. A., & S D. Hyperopia in young people: risk factors and prognosis at the CADES/O of the Donka National Hospital Guinea. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*. 2022; 5(8): 2135–2144.